

Green Management as a Predictor of Organizational Outcomes in Hospitality Enterprises in Mbaise

Njoku K. C^{1*}, Udo-Orji C² and Anyanwu R. C³.

¹Department of Business Administration, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State.

²Department of Marketing, Kinsley Ozumba Mbadiwe University, Ideato, Imo State

³Department of General Studies, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences(UAES), Umuagwo, Imo State.

**Corresponding author: Kenneth.njoku@uaes.edu.ng*

Received: October 19, 2023; Accepted: April 1, 2024 ; Published: April 22, 2024.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11021458

Abstract: The study assesses green management and organizational outcomes in hospitality firms in Mbaise. The objectives of the study are to evaluate the level of correlation between pollution control and market share; assess the level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention; examine the level of correlation between waste management and market share; and to determine the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. The research adopts the survey research design. The validity of the questionnaire was carried out by attracting the inputs of specialists in research for their corrections and professional contributions. The reliability ratio of the survey instrument was 0.72. To analyze data, descriptive statistics was used. It uses Spearman Product Moment correlation analysis to test hypotheses. The paper reveals that pollution control and market share; pollution control and employee retention; waste management and market share; waste management and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise, have positive and significant relationships. The study concludes that green management improves organizational outcomes in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. The researchers recommend that management of hospitality firms should make more efforts to control all forms of pollution in the enterprises for improved market share and employee retention. Waste to wealth strategy should be employed by hospitality firms for improved organizational outcomes. Hospitality firms in Mbaise should always seriously embrace green management.

Keywords: *Green management, Organizational outcomes, Hospitality.*

Introduction

Background of the Study

It is a truism that any corporate entity that desires sound organizational outcomes no doubt sees sustainability as its watchword. This is the central focus of green management. Green management as a concept has been widely discussed by researchers especially in recent times. Sah (2023) is of the view that green management is a way of applying environmental considerations into corporate decision-making procedure or process. It pays great attention to adopting sustainability in the conduct of business and its practices with a view to curbing unfavourable and bad impacts on the environment while conserving resources and encouraging eco-friendly business practices. Elshaer, Azazz and Fayyad (2023) are of the view that green management focuses on conscious and intentional prevention of pollution, waste and emissions.

This research focuses on pollution control and waste management aspects of green management. Pollution is generally seen as a situation whereby harmful substances are introduced into the environment. Nathanson (2023) maintains that pollution can be air, water or land pollution. This agrees with the position of Robb (2021) who asserts that pollution is the consequence of contaminating

the air, water and/or land with various kinds of materials. These materials can be chemicals; they may be trash or other substances. The WHO (2023) describes air pollution as that health threat that is quite invisible and it is a public health emergency. WHO reveals that air pollution is just less fatal than hypertension and the smoking of tobacco in addition to the dangers of high glucose. Nathanson (2023) sees land pollution as a situation whereby solid or liquid waste items are deposited on land or even underground in a harmful manner capable of contaminating the soil and groundwater while posing a threat to public health and leading to nuisances and creation of eye sores and/or unsightly conditions. In the same vein, water pollution, according to Denchak (2023) occurs when harmful substances contaminate water bodies thereby causing it to be toxic to human beings or the environment.

Pollution control has become a major environmental and green management issue in Nigeria. Efforts have been observed to have been made by different key players in the national economy to control pollution in Nigeria. Pollution control represents the reduction or elimination of the release of harmful substances into the environment (Smarter, 2023). Olugbode (2023) reveals that the Federal Government of Nigeria has

introduced the National Generator Emission Control Programme (NGECP) as well as the National Vehicular Emission Control Programme (NVECP) for the purpose of combating air pollution in the nation. Ayeyemi (2023) reveals that in Nigeria, there are attempts to ban the use of plastics hence the meeting of various stakeholders in Lagos for the purpose of reviewing the draft National Environmental (Plastic waste Control) Regulation, 2023. Also, Odeniyi (2023) maintains that the 51.35% of Hydro chlorofluorocarbons consumption would be phased out by the end of 2023 hence they are chemical compounds which the foam, refrigerator and air conditioning sectors use and they destroy the protective ozone layer while contributing to climate change. Indeed, Akindele (2022) opines that businesses, individual persons, communities and governments have roles to play in fighting pollution in the environment. Pollution is dangerous to business. In fact, Tiamiyu (2023) opines that polluting with plastic wastes adversely affects tourism activities and the entire economic sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Another index of green management which this study evaluates is waste management. The general idea of waste management is the disposal of wastes, reducing of wastes,

reusing of wastes and preventing of wastes. Tayo (2023) reports that one of the most significant problems facing the Giant of Africa is the problem of waste management. The Africa's biggest economy, according to Tayo (2023) generates per annum, thirty-two million tonnes of solid waste. An insignificant percentage of the waste generated in Nigeria is recycled. Allen-Taylor (2023) describes waste disposal in the Africa's largest economy (Nigeria) as a mess. Nigeria lacks accurate and documented data over the quality of waste she generates. This is despite the fact that the Nigerian National Municipal Waste Management Policy has the capacity for managing wastes efficiently in Nigeria. It is however worrisome that waste management in Nigeria is yet to be managed in a way that showcases sustainability. Nkwocha, Phil-Eze, Shettima, Ihekumere and Zulum (2023) reveal that the management of solid waste in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria is not adequate hence there are infrastructural gaps and inappropriate water disposal practices in addition to poor public awareness. Its waste management policies to remain alive instead of doing away with them. Idowu-Adegoke and Beinisch (2023) maintain that President Tinubu suspended a ten per cent tax plan in the form of green taxation on plastics used once known as single-use plastics which

former Nigerian Leader Mr Buhari introduced in fifth month of 2023 as he was about leaving office; a development seen by environmental groups as unfortunate. Worrying situations of this kind may have prompted institutions like the Nigerian Institute of Town Planners to call on the public authorities to create a plan with the objective of receiving and managing of plastic waste in Nigeria as revealed by Ogundeji (2023).

Waste management has become so serious in Nigeria that different groups have started creating waste management awareness in critical Nigerian cities. Mojeed (2023) opines that the staff of the Center for Journalism Innovation and Development (CJID) in collaboration with other entities on World Cleanup Day, 2023 sensitized the public at the streets of Abuja on plastic waste management and climate change. There is also a challenge with management of waste in the country's (Nigeria's) neighborhoods with income levels that are quite low and where many businesses also exist. Agbo (2023) maintains that for three decades now, major cities in the Nigerian nation have continued to speedily urbanize. This leads to a lot of rural-urban migration hence people look for greener pasture. Agbo asserts that the World Bank reports serious population growth in

Nigerian urban cities hence high volume of wastes are generated. This is confirmed by the Nigerian Institute of Town Planners (2023) which asserts that it is unarguable that the rates of waste generation are on the increase in the most populous black nation. Udensi, Anyanwu, Opara, Okafor, Duru and Emenonu (2023) opine that most persons dispose waste by themselves and most of the wastes are dumped in the gutter/drains while little is dumped by roadsides and approved dumpsites. These persons include individual and corporate persons which may include hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Green management may have the capacity to influence organizational outcomes in hospitality-based firms. Organizational outcomes as used in this research means the use of pollution control and waste management to enhance market share and employee retention. Each industry normally has total industry sales. The percent of the aggregate industry sales that a firm has is its market share. March (2023) opines that with market share, a business actually measures its success within the market. Sales revenue is used to determine market share, and it is normally evaluated within a fiscal year or quarter. Burgess (2023) opines that businesses that enjoy high level of market share often become very profitable and profit-wise, they

are often better than their rivals. There are also factors that improve market share or market value. Raphel, Edet and Nduonofit (2023) assert that return on assets and firm size influence market value of companies. Also, Emudainohwo and Tarurhor (2023) opine that accounting information enhances market share value of equity in Nigeria. Indeed, Etim, Umoffong, Inyang and Umanah (2023) maintain that the factors that influence market share and/or earnings quality of a firm include managerial ownership, firm size and liquidity. It is therefore ideal to believe with Bhattacharya, Morgan and Rego (2023) that market share remains a product of an entity's marketing efforts which comprises the firms advertising, promotion, quality of products, its pricing strategies, its customer relationships and its sales activities.

Employee retention is another index of organizational outcomes. It is the ability which an organization has to retain its own workers. The retention of employees is the opposite of employee turnover. Beasley and Que (2023) states that in employee retention, an organization prevents its staff from leaving the organization. To do this, the organization must make employee pay to be competitive; give orientation to the worker; ensure that job description and, job expectations are unambiguously clear and ensure open and

transparent communication. There ought to be a prioritization of work-life balance, performance reviews, growth opportunities, inclusive work environment, employee recognition, employee promotion and stay interviews. Njoku, Donatus and Salamatu (2023) maintain that employee retention can be influenced by employee recognition. Employee retention can also be influenced by sensitivity training and team building. Indeed, Njoku and Uzodimma (2023) opine that sensitivity training and team building are correlates of employee retention and they seriously influence employee retention. In fact, Awolaja (2023) reveals that the employee retention strategies include opportunities for growth in the job, compensation arrangement that is competitive as well as sound balance between work and life. Also, Musa, Ahmed, Hamza (2023) maintain that the employee retention strategies include organizational justice, work-life balance, training and development, the support of the supervisors and job satisfaction. Reasoning in the same direction, Odunukwe and Nnanyelugo (2023) maintain that employee turnover often has a link with the way employee compensation is managed. This calls for effective compensation regimes for improved employee retention.

The study focuses in Mbaise. The reasons for focusing on Mbaise include that no visible empirical study conducted in Nigeria in the area of green management has ever been done in Mbaise. This situation was discovered after the researchers had carefully searched various sources that showcase studies that are visible to the global research community especially online sources like google. This is a worrisome situation that shows a deep research gap hence this study. Another reason is that the rate of establishment of industrial entities and indeed hospitality enterprises in Mbaise clan has been noticed by the researchers to have continued to increase in recent times – a development that requires the adoption of green management options for sustainability and desirable organizational outcomes. This study therefore on green management as a predictor of organizational outcomes in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise is geared towards investigating how the hospitality firms handle pollution and wastes for increased market share and employee retention. This is with a view to bridging research gaps and contributing to knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

Any organization that values sustainability in its operations may unarguably never toy with green management practices for enhanced

organizational outcomes. This is both a fact and the ideal situation. However, it is quite worrisome that many business organizations have been observed by the researcher to have relegated green management practices to the background and such attitude is feared to have adversely influenced corporate outcomes. This ugly situation cannot be to the best interest of the enterprises.

Business organizations have been observed by Akindele (2022) to have consistently polluted the environment in which they carry out their operations and a lot of land pollution and air pollution have been observed to be the lot of many enterprises in both the rural and urban areas. Some of the firms neither consider the health and safety of their workers and customers nor that of the residents of their host communities. Firms in various industries have been further observed to have failed to recycle their waste products in the form of waste to wealth. Many of the enterprises are foreign to the reuse aspect of waste management and they have not been observed to have taken any safe measure in destroying or disposing wastes (Allen-Taylor, 2023; Elshaver, 2023; Idowu-Adegoke and Beinisch, 2023).

Empirical works on green management which the researchers consulted did not indicate or

show how pollution control influenced market share and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. The studies did not also show how waste management influenced market share and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise. Evidences abound. For example, Alao, Adegbe and Joshua (2023) did a research in the area of environmental sustainability. Goni, Binti, Isa and Abdullah (2023) did a study in the area of green innovation in Kano. Also, Soyeye, Makinde and Akanlabi (2023) concentrated in Lagos in their study in the area of green supply chain management. They did not pay attention to green management issues in Mbaise. These evidences show that a research gap exists. It is therefore the research gap discovered by the researchers that constitutes the problem of this study.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of the research is to investigate green management as a predictor of organizational outcomes in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. The study was specifically conducted to:

- i. evaluate the level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.
- ii. assess the level of correlation between pollution control and employee

retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

- iii. examine level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.
- iv. determine the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Research Questions

The research questions below guide this study:

- i. What is the level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise?
- ii. What is the level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise?
- iii. What is the level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise?
- iv. What is the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise?

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses for the study are as shown below:

H₀₁: There is no significant level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise

H₀₂: There is no significant level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise

H₀₃: There is no significant level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms. in Mbaise

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on selected hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. Mbaise constitutes the geographical area which the study covers. The research evaluates the link between control of pollution and market share; pollution control and employee retention; waste management and market share; waste management and employee retention in Mbaise. The unit scope

consists of all the functional units in the study hospitality enterprises. For the time scope, it took the researchers a period of three months to handle this study.

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Review

The study employed the following theories in the study:

Icek Ajzen Theory of Planned Behaviour

Icek Ajzen theory of planned behavior which sees behavior as a product of intentions and attitudes which are basically beliefs about a behavior as well as subjective norms which are beliefs about the attitudes of others toward behavior, has remained a popular theory in Management literatures. It was propounded in 1985. The theory predicts human behavior on the basis of personal attitudes; on the basis of subjective norms and on the basis of behavioural control as may be perceived. Bosnjak, Ajzen and Schmidt (2020) opine that human behavior is directed with the instrument of believes that are behavioural; believes that are normative as well as believes that are called control beliefs. Belief that is behavioural is that which has to do with the behavioural outcomes of the behavior. Believes that are described as normative have to do with those believes that anchor on the

expectations of other people. These expectations are the normative ones. The beliefs referred to as 'control beliefs' are those ones that include forces or factors which boost or incapacitate performing the behavior. LaMorte (2022) maintains that this theory has over the years, been appropriately used to forecast and/or give explanation of various behaviours. The theory supposes that behavioural achievement is a function of motivation which is the intention as well as ability which is the behavioural control. The model is characterized by 6 (six) dimensions that altogether indicate one's real control over the behavior. Indeed, the dimensions are: attitudes, behavioural intention, subjective norms, social norms, perceived power and perceived behavioural control. In fact, this theory relates to this study which emphasizes pollution control and waste management. People ought to exhibit sound behaviours over issues of pollution, waste and even environmental health.

Empirical Review

The following empirical studies were used to boost the study:

Soyeye, Makinde and Akinlabi (2023) examined green supply chain management and organizational performance of fast moving consumer goods firms in Lagos

Nigeria. It was a survey research. Data analysis was committed to multiple regressions, Cronbach Alpha and descriptive statistics. It was found that green supply chain management had positive and significant effect on the performance of fast-moving consumer goods companies in Lagos.

Asubiojo, Dagundoro and Falana (2023) evaluated environmental conservation cost and corporate performance of quarry companies in Nigeria: an empirical analysis. It was a survey research. A structured questionnaire was their major instrument for data collection. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. It was found that research and development, legal and regulatory compliance costs exhibited a significant positive relationship with the corporate performance of quarry firms in Nigeria. Su, Bei-Bei, Shan, Xu and Jin-Long (2023) did an empirical analysis of green finance and high-quality economic development in the Yangtze River Delta based on VAR and coupling coordination model. It was an ex post facto study. VAR, gray correlation method and gray prediction method were used for data analysis. It was found that green finance has short-term mutual promotion effects with high-quality economic development. It was recommended

that more professionals need to be involved in green finance innovation.

Li, Wang and Nutakor (2023) did an empirical research on the influence of corporate digitalization on green innovation. They used ex post facto research design. Resource-based theory was employed. Regression analysis was used for data analysis. It was found that corporate digitalization improved green innovation by improving human capital. It was concluded that enterprises that boost their digital strategies do better in green innovation. It was recommended that organizations need to encourage green innovation for sustainable business development.

Elshaer, Azazz and Fayyad (2023) evaluated green management and sustainable performance of small and medium-sized hospitality businesses: moderating the role of an employee's pro-environmental behavior. It was a survey research. The study used the Smart PLS-structural equation modelling technique to analyze data. It was found that green management improved environmental, economic and social performance of businesses. It was recommended that enterprises should concentrate on creating the culture of environmental stewardships and

involvement in green initiatives for improved sustainable corporate outcomes.

Goni, Binti, Isa and Abdullah (2023) investigated green innovations and environmental performance of hotels in Kano, Nigeria: moderating role of green transformational leadership. It was a survey research. PLS-SEM was used for data analysis. It was found that green innovation positively and significantly influenced environmental performance of Kano-based hotels. The study concludes that green innovations affects environmental performance. It was recommended that management should use facilities that do not expose the environment to pollutions.

Alao, Adegbe and Joshua (2023) examined green intellectual capital and environmental sustainability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It was a research. Multiple regression was used to handle data analysis. It was found that green intellectual capital positively and significantly influenced environmental sustainability. It was recommended that corporate entities need to invest in environmental systems.

Wiredu, Agyemang and Agbadzidah (2023) handled the topic: Does green accounting influence ecological sustainability: evidence from a developing economy? The survey

research design was used in the study that focused on pharmaceutical enterprises. Data analysis was committed to PLS-SEM and SMART-PLS 4 was used to test hypotheses. It was found that environmental compliance and business efficiency have major and constructive effect on sustainability.

Osaloni and Oso (2023) did an evaluation of environmental accounting information and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It was an ex post facto research. Data analysis was committed to descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis. It was found that environmental accounting information had a significant influence on the financial performance of the manufacturing enterprises. It was recommended that manufacturing firms should make investments in ecological development a top priority.

Ali, Gyamfi, Bekun, Ozturk and Nketiah (2023) did an empirical assessment of the tripartite nexus between environmental pollution, economic growth and agricultural production in sub-Saharan African countries. It was an ex post facto research. It employed the panel econometrics method of the generalized method of moments (two-step difference GMM). It was found that economic growth contributes significantly to

environmental pollution in Africa. Food Price Index capital and FDI enhance pollution. Also, agricultural production and labour reduce pollution.

Si and Tiwari (2023) did a study on understanding the green procurement behavior of household appliance manufacturing industry: an empirical study of the enablers. It is a survey research. Data analysis was committed to Structural Equation Model(SEM). The findings show that exogenous driving powers are more inclined to encourage household appliance manufacturers to perform green procurement strategy compared with endogenous factors. Business strategy, governmental regulations and customer awareness show greater influence on green purchasing behavior unlike the little impact of corporate culture, production system and suppliers. Taxation policies, environmental awareness and green strategies are the key driving forces for promoting green procurement from the government, individual and organizational dimensions.

Njoku, Donatus; and Salamatu (2023) examined employee recognition as a correlate of employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Owerri. It was a survey research. Their study employed the Kenneth Chukwudi

Njoku's Ken-C theory of Social Honour. Data analysis was committed to descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Spearman product moment correlation coefficient was used to test hypotheses. It was found that public recognition, monetary recognition and promotional recognition positively and significantly influenced employee retention in hospitality enterprises. The researchers concluded that employee recognition influenced employee retention in the enterprises.

Njoku and Uzodimma (2023) conducted a study on organizational development and corporate outcomes in Owerri-based health facilities. It was a survey research. Data analysis was committed to descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Spearman product moment correlation was used to test hypotheses. It was found that sensitivity training and team building positively and significantly influenced employee retention and capacity expansion.

Gap Identified in Literature

The gap identified in literature is that various empirical researches that the researchers accessed in the area of green management did not show how each of pollution control and waste management influenced market share

and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Methodology

The researchers used the survey research design in the research. The managers and workers of 10 hospitality firms in Mbaise constituted the population of the study. The firms were purposively chosen. The reason for choosing the firms is that they were very accessible to the researchers. Also, issues of insecurity and bad roads could not allow the researchers to access certain remote parts of Mbaise where other hospitality enterprises exist. Given that almost all the hospitality enterprises were small scale guest houses, the firms had average staff strength of 15 staff each and this includes the manager and very few assistants. The enterprises assessed were not too formally structured but their services had a lot to do with issues of green management especially pollution control and waste management. The study population was therefore 150. The researchers used the Taro Yamen's formula for sample size determination to obtain a sample size of 109 for the study. Accordingly, the researchers administered one hundred and nine (109) copies of the research instrument to the respondents in the study hospitality firms. Data sources included both primary and

secondary sources. While the questionnaire was the major instrument of collection of data which was used for the study, the researchers relied on texts, journals and internet sources for secondary data. Indeed, the research instrument validity was handled by involving experts in research who made useful contributions that made it possible for the study to focus on the stated research questions. The reliability of the study instrument namely the questionnaire was done by adoption of a pilot study whose results were committed to Cronbach alpha statistic. A ratio of 0.72 was

obtained thereby making the instrument to be reliable to the degree of 72%. The study employed mean and standard deviation statistics for data analysis. Spearman Product Moment Correlation analysis was used to test hypotheses. The null hypothesis was rejected on the basis of $P < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Out of the 109 questionnaire copies distributed to the respondents, only 85 copies were properly filled and returned. This means 78% return.

Research Question 1:

What is the level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms?

Table 1 Pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise

Qs/ No	Item	S.A	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Pollution control attracts more customers to the hospitality firm hence improved market share.	41	28	7	4	5	85	4.13	0.712
2	Pollution control creates very cordial relationship between the firm and immediate environment hence sound patronage from the host community to the hospitality firm.	38	25	9	7	6	85	3.96	0.749

Field Survey (2023)

The table above shows the level of relationship between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise. The results indicates that that: pollution control attracts more customers to the hospitality firm hence improved market

share ($\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.13 ± 0.712); pollution control creates very cordial relationship between the firm and immediate environment hence sound patronage from

the host community to the hospitality firm
(with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 3.96 ± 0.749).

Research Question 2:

What is the level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms?

Table 2: Pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms

Q/ No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
3	Pollution control helps to avert employee turnover in hospitality firms..	40	29	8	5	3	85	4.15	0.804
4	Management budgets for effective pollution control each year to the admiration of employees whose health and safety are protected by such gesture..	32	21	20	9	3	85	3.82	0.813

Field Survey (2023)

The table shows the level of relationship between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms. It shows that pollution control helps to avert employee turnover in hospitality firms as the result accounted for a mean of 3.82 and a standard deviation of 0.813. And management budgets for effective pollution control each year to the admiration of employees whose

health and safety are protected by such gesture (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 3.69 ± 0.788).

Research Question 3:

What is the level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms?

Report on Research Question 3 is presented on Table 3.

Table 3: Waste management and market share in hospitality firms

Q/ No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
5	Sound waste management improves the customer base and market share of	29	26	14	7	9	85	3.69	0.788

hospitality firms.										
6	Management punishes workers who are indifferent to effective waste management so as to always improve market share.	31	21	17	11	5	85	3.73	0.851	

Field Survey (2023)

The table above shows the level of relationship between waste management and market share in hospitality firms. It shows that that: sound waste management improves the customer base and market share of hospitality firms with a ($\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 3.69 ± 0.788) ; management punishes workers who are indifferent to effective

waste management so as to always improve market share (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 3.73 ± 0.851).

Research Question 4:

What is the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms?

Table 4: Waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms

Q/ No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
7	Waste management is a strategic tool for employee retention in hospitality firms.	36	24	19	4	2	85	4.04	0.866
8	Some employees assist management in waste management practices and as a result, resolve to stay longer with the hospitality firm.	33	27	21	2	2	85	4.02	0.793

Field Survey (2023)

The above table shows the relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms. The table shows that waste management is a strategic

tool for employee retention in hospitality firms as the result accounted for a mean of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.866. And some employees assist management in waste

management practices and as a result, resolve to stay longer with the hospitality firm (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.02 ± 0.793).

Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Table 5: Correlation analysis between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Pollution control	4.13	0.712	0.822	0.001
Market share	3.96	0.749		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2023).

The result on Table 5 presents the correlation analysis between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Owerri Municipal. The result shows a p-value of 0.001 and correlation coefficient of 0.822. The result shows a p-value less than 0.05 being the level of significance; therefore, rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, the correlation coefficient

between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise is statistically significant. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

H₀₂: There is no significant level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Table 6: Correlation analysis between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Pollution control	4.15	0.804	0.743	0.001
Employee retention	3.82	0.813		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2023).

The result on Table 6 presents the correlation analysis between pollution

control and employee retention in hospitality firms. The result shows a p-value of 0.001

and correlation coefficient of 0.743. The result shows a p – value ≤ 0.05 level of significance, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative which states that there is a significant level of correlation between pollution control and

employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

H₀₃: There is no significant level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Table 7: Correlation analysis between waste management and market share in hospitality firms

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Waste management	3.69	0.788	0.807	0.001
Market share	3.73	0.851		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2023).

The result on Table 7 presents the correlation analysis between waste management and market share in hospitality firms. The result shows a p-value of 0.001 and correlation coefficient of 0.807. The result shows a p-value less ≤ 0.05 level of significance; therefore, rejecting the null

hypothesis and accepting the alternative which states that there is a significant relationship between waste management and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Table 8: Correlation analysis between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Waste management	4.04	0.866	0.809	0.001
Employee retention	4.02	0.793		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2023).

The result on Table 8 presents the correlation analysis between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms. The result shows a p-value

of 0.001 and correlation coefficient of 0.809. The result shows a p-value less ≤ 0.05 level of significance; therefore, rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative

which states that there is a significant relationship between waste management and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Discussion

The fact that pollution control attracts more customers to the hospitality firms hence improved market share as shown on table 1 indicates that customers are conscious of their health even as they patronize the hospitality enterprises. It also indicates that organizational management in the study businesses are socially responsible to invoke cordial relationships with their host communities via the instrumentality of pollution control. The study by Elshaer, et al (2023) in the area of green management is relevant here. It was a survey research. It was found that green management improved performance environmentally, economically and socially for businesses. It was recommended that enterprises should be conscious of the environment for improved sustainable corporate outcomes. This is in agreement with the findings made the present research.

Given that pollution control helps to avert employee turnover in hospitality firms in Mbaise as shown on table 2, it implies that workers in the enterprises are not victims of

noise pollution, water pollution and land pollution. This may be because the organizational management arms itself with good budgets for effective pollution control as the table 2 reveals. This no doubt speaks volumes about the sound attitude of the organizations to the welfare and health of their workers. This can be a way of recognizing the value of the workers and such recognition can encourage employee retention. Njoku, et al (2023) examined employee recognition and employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Owerri. It was a survey research. Their study employed the Ken-C theory of Social Honour. Data analysis was done with mean and standard deviation statistics. Spearman product moment correlation coefficient was used to test hypotheses. It was found that public recognition, monetary recognition and promotional recognition positively and significantly influenced employee retention in hospitality enterprises. The researchers concluded that employee recognition influenced employee retention in the enterprises. This is in agreement with the findings made the present research. Also, Goni, et al (2023) did a study in the area of green innovations. It was a survey research. It was found that green innovation improved environmental performance of Kano-based

hotels. This aligns with the findings in this study.

It is interesting to discover that sound waste management improved the customer base and market share of hospitality firms. This is as table 3 shows. The implication of this revelation in the study is that management re-uses its business wastes; management values recycling and management disposes wastes responsibly. It is important to note at this point in time that reuse of wastes can boost backward integration as observed by Njoku, Donatus and Uchechukwu (2023). It is good to discover that management punishes workers who are indifferent to effective waste management for the sake of improving market share in the enterprises just as table 3 indicates.

The fact that waste management is a strategic tool for employee retention in hospitality firms as shown on table 4 implies that quality employees perform above board in waste-to-wealth-focused enterprises. This is further supported by the fact that there are workers who assist management in waste management practices and consequently, decide to remain even longer with the organization. The study by Njoku, et al (2023) on employee recognition agrees with the findings in this study. Also, Alao, et al

(2023) did a study in the area of green intellectual capital. Multiple regression was used to handle data analysis. It was found that green intellectual capital positively and significantly influenced environmental sustainability. It was recommended that corporate entities need to invest in environmental systems. It is also a truism that environmental sustainability is a core thrust of waste management efforts. This therefore aligns with the findings in this present study.

Findings

Sequel to analysis of numerical data, it was found that:

- i. There is a significant level of correlation between pollution control and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.
- ii. There is a significant level of correlation between pollution control and employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.
- iii. There is a significant level of correlation between waste management and market share in hospitality firms in Mbaise.
- iv. There is a significant relationship between waste management and

employee retention in hospitality firms in Mbaise.

Conclusion

This study concludes that green management improves organizational outcomes in hospitality enterprises in Mbaise. Pollution control is essential for the good of both the customers and the employees hence it boosts market share and employee retention. Waste management is a critical element in the practice of green management by organizations hence it enhances market share while retarding employee turnover in favour of employee retention. The study therefore submits that any organization that relegates the green management practices of pollution control and waste management to the background makes itself vulnerable to avoidable performance crisis.

The researcher further infers that this study contributes to knowledge by providing empirical literature and by bridging research gaps on the relationships between each of

pollution control and waste management and each of market share employee retention. The study also adds to the already existing body of knowledge as it concerns the field of green management.

Recommendations

The researchers developed the following recommendations:

- i. Management of hospitality firms should make more efforts to control all forms of pollution in the enterprises for improved market share.
- ii. Management of hospitality firms should manage all forms of pollution in the enterprises for prudently for enhanced employee retention.
- iii. Waste to wealth strategy should be employed by hospitality firms so as to boost market share.
- iv. Hospitality firms in Mbaise should embrace waste management more seriously in other to beef up their employee retention efforts.

References

- Agbo, M. (2023). "The problem with solid waste management in Nigeria's low-income neighborhoods" from earth.org. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Akindele, E.O. (2022). "Nigeria's plastic pollution is harming the environment: steps to combat it are overdue" from conservation.com. Retrieved 13/09/23.

- Alao, E.M., Adegbe, F.F., and Joshua, A.A. (2023). Green intellectual capital and environmental sustainability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 27(55): 1-14.
- Ali, E.B., Gyamfi, B.A., Bekun, F.V., Ozturk, I., and Nketiah, P. (2023). An empirical assessment of the ripartite nexus between environmental pollution, economic growth and agricultural production in sub-Saharan African countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30, 71007-71024.
- Allen-Taylor, K. (2023). "Waste disposal in Nigeria is a mess: How Lagos can take the lead in sorting and recycling" from phys.org. Retrieved 17/09/23.
- Asubiojo, A.O., Dagunduro, M.E., and Falana, G.A. (2023). Environmental conservation cost and corporate performance of quarry companies in Nigeria: an empirical analysis. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences* 7(8): 49-63.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2023.7804>.
- Awolaja, A.M. (2023). Employee retention strategies and organizational performance among academic staff of selected private universities in Osun State Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Banking and Financial Issues*, 9(1): 157-169.
- Ayeyemi, D. (2023). "Stakeholders express views on draft plastic waste control regulation" from uneonline.com. Retrieved 10/09/23.
- Beasley, C., and Que, G. (2023). "Employee retention: 14 strategies to keep your top talent in 2023" from smallbusiness.com. Retrieved 13/09/23.
- Bhattacharya, A., Morgan, N.A., and Rego, L.L. (2023). Examining why and when market share drives firm profit. *Journal of Marketing*, 86(4): 73-94.
doi:10.1177/00222429211031922.
- Bosnjak, M., Ajzen, I., and Schmidst, P. (2020). The theory of planned behavior: selected recent advances and applications. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 16(3):352-356;
doi:10.5964/ejop.v16i3.3107.
- Burgess, J. (2023). "What is market share and why should we care?" from sogolitics.com. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Denchak, M. (2023). "Water pollution: everything you need to know" from nrdc.org. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Elshaer, I.A., Azazz, A.M.S., and Fayyad, S. (2023). Green management and sustainable performance of small and medium-sized hospitality businesses: moderating the role of an employee's pro-environmental behavior. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3): 2244;
doi:10.3390/ijerph20032244.
- Emudainohwo, O.B., and Tarurhor, E. (2023). "Impact of Accounting information on market value of equity in Nigeria" from researchgate.net. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Etim, E.O., Umoffong, N.J., Inyang, A.B., and Umanah, N. (2023). Determinants of earnings quality of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. *Asian*

- Journal of Economics and Finance, 5(2): 231-248.
- Goni, K.M., Binti, Y.Z., Isa, M., and Abdullah, T.B. (2023). Green innovations and environmental performance of hotels in Kano, Nigeria: moderating role of green transformational leadership. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 11(3): doi.10.4236/jhrss.2023.113036.
- Idowu-Adegoke, F., and Beinisch, N. (2023). “Nigeria’s Plastic waste management policies should not be trashed” from *businessday.ng*. Retrieved 11/09/23.
- LaMorte, W.W. (2022). “Behavioural change models: the theory of Planned Behaviour” from *web.bumc.bu.edu*. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Li, J., Wang, L., and Nutakor, F. (2023). Empirical research on the influence of corporate digitalization on green innovation. *Environmental Economics and Management*, Volume 11; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvo.2023.1137271>.
- March, L. (2023). “What is market share: Definition, formulas and examples” from *similarweb.com*. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Mojeed, A. (2023). “World cleanup day 2023: Groups take waste management awareness to Abuja streets” from *premiumtimesng.com*. Retrieved 15/09/23.
- Musa, B.M., Ahmed, I., and Hamza, H.D. (2023). Workers’ retention strategies in Nigeria: A review. *ILIMI Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 2(1): 54-63.
- Nathanson, J.A. (2023). “Land pollution” from *Britannica.com*. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Nathanson, J.A. (2023). “Pollution” from *Britannica.com*. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- NITP (2023). “World Environment Day 2023 – Towards evolving solutions to plastic pollution in Nigeria: Urban planning perspective” from *nitpng.org*. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Njoku, K.C., and Uzodimma, E.E. (2023). Organizational development and corporate outcomes in Owerri-based health facilities. *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 60(2): 160-171.
- Njoku, K.C., Donatus, E.A., and Salamatu, I. (2023). Employee recognition as a correlate of employee retention in hospitality enterprises in Owerri. *International Journal of African Sustainable Development Research*, 14(2): 53-62.
- Njoku, K.C., Donatus, E.A., and Uchechukwu, A.C. (2023). “Green management and performance of hospitality firms in Owerri Municipal” – A Paper Presented At the MONA International Conference of Hospitality, Tourism and Management At University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, October, 6.
- Odeniyi, S. (2023). “Nigeria to phase out 51% HCFC in 2023 – Environment Minister” from *punchng.com*. Retrieved 11/09/23.
- Odonukwe, I.E., and Nnanyelugo, N.T. (2023). Compensation management and employee turnover in plastic manufacturing firms in Anambra State. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 3(8): 16-35.

- Ogundeji, J. (2023). "Institute advocates waste management policy" from punchng.com. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Olugbode, M. (2023). "FG introduces initiative to reduce air pollution" from thisdaylive.com. Retrieved 11/09/23.
- Osaloni, B.O., and Oso, O.O. (2023). An evaluation of environmental accounting information and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 3(2):1055-1064.
- Raphel, E., Edet, J.P., and Nduonofit, C.B. (2023). Empirical investigation of firms' characteristics on market value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities*, 2(1): 96-120. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7970810.
- Robb, A. (2021). "What is pollution? - Lesson for kids: Definition and facts" from study.com. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Sah, N. (2023). "Exploring green management: A comprehensive guide to sustainable business practices" from linkedin.com. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Si, D., and Tiwari, S. (2023). Understanding the green procurement behavior of household appliance manufacturing industry: an empirical study of the enablers. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, Volume 2023; Article ID 9719019, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9719019>.
- Smarter, S. (2023). "Pollutant control" from studysmarter.co.uk. Retrieved 12/09/23.
- Soyeye, S.O.O., Makinde, G.O., and Akanlabi, B.H. (2023). Green supply chain management and organizational performance of fast-moving consumer goods firms in Lagos Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 6(2): 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.47672/ije.1517>.
- Su, Z., Bei-Bei, L., Shan-Zhi, X., and Jin-Long, H. (2023). Empirical analysis of green finance and high-quality economic development in the Yangtze River Delta based on VAR and coupling coordination model. *Environmental Economics and Management*, Volume 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1211174>.
- Tayo, O. (2023). "Zero waste day 2023: Why Nigeria must prioritise recycling by Tayo Olu" from arareporters.com.
- Tiamiyu, T. (2023). "Plastic waste pollution in the Nigerian tourism sector – Who is responsible?" from emerald.com. Retrieved 12/09/23.
- Udensi, J.U., Anyanwu, C.O., Opara, M.C., Okafor, J.C., Duru, C.C., and Emenonu, O. (2023). Assessment of solid waste management methods in some selected parts of Owerri West, Imo State, Nigeria. *Archives of Current Research International*, 23(6): 1-10.
- WHO (2023). "Air pollution: The invisible health threat" from who.int. Retrieved 09/09/23.
- Wiredu, I., Agyemang, A.O., and Agbadzidah S.Y. (2023). Does green accounting influence ecological sustainability: evidence from a developing economy? *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(2).

<https://doi.org/10.1080/2311975.2023.2240559>.